

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Ar	Solvent		m.p. °C	Yield%		M.F.	Analysis% Found/(Calcd.)	
		Ac	Alc		Ac	Alc		C	H
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	Ac	Alc	124	50	73	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O	89.9 (89.36)	5.1 (4.965)
2.	p-NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ -	..	..	181	60	80.0	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ ON	77.04 (77.06)	3.97 (3.91)
3.	C ₆ H ₅ - CH=CH -	..	..	112	—	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O	77.1 (77.06)	3.99 (3.97)
4.	p-CH ₃ O - C ₆ H ₄ -	..	..	282	—	70	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂	84.66 (84.61)	5.16 (5.12)
5.	o-HO - C ₆ H ₄ -	..	..	232	45	—	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	84.5 (84.56)	4.9 (4.7)

Ac—Acetic anhydride; Alc—Alcohol

(λ_{max} in nm) were recorded in methanol, ir spectra (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) in KBr pellets and nmr (chemical shifts in δ_{ppm}) using TMS as a standard.

Preparation of 10-arylidene anthrone (Table I): Equimolar quantities of anthrone and suitably substituted aldehydes (0.001 mole) were taken in acetic anhydride (20-25 ml) with 2-3 drops of piperidine. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 hr, poured into cold saturated NaHCO₃ solution, filtered, and washed with water. The solid was then dried and crystallised from suitable solvents. In the second method an identical procedure was followed except that in place of acetic anhydride alcohol was used as the solvent: uv 368; ir 1655 ($>C=O$), 1595 ($>C=C$); nmr 7.1 (s, $>C=C$), 7.4–8.23 (m, Ar-H).

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Rare Flavone-C-Glycosides from

Mollugo cerviana

A. G. RAMACHANDRAN NAIR

and

R. GUNASEGARAN

Chemical Laboratories, Jawaharlal Institute,
Pondicherry-605 006

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THE genus *Mollugo* included till recently in the betalin family Aizoaceae¹, has been separated and taken into the new anthocyanin family Molluginaceae² in the same order, Centrospermae. As a part of chemotaxonomic studies on *Mollugo*, we

have screened³ the flavonoid constituents of six *Mollugo* species (*M. disticha*, *M. pentaphylla*, *M. nudicaulis*, *M. cerviana*, *M. lotoides* and *M. oppositifolia*) and found that all of them contained flavone-C-glycosides and were devoid of 6-oxygenated flavones. In continuation of our report on the occurrence of new flavone-C-glycosides in *M. disticha*³ and *M. pentaphylla*⁴, we present here the isolation and characterisation of four flavone-C-glycosides including two rare ones (orientin-2"-O-glucoside and vitexin-2"-O-glucoside) from *M. cerviana*.

Experimental

Fresh whole plants of *M. cerviana* were collected from Pondicherry and worked up for flavonoids according to standard procedures³⁻⁵. The flavone-C-glycosides extracted from the aqueous alcoholic concentrate by partition with ethyl methyl ketone or butanol were subjected to three-stage separation (column chromatography over silica, preparative paper chromatography and thin layer chromatography over silica) to yield four tlc homogeneous compounds, A–D, which were studied by uv fluorescence, colour reactions, λ_{max} , m.p., R_f , products of acid hydrolysis and characterised as follows.

Compound A: Yellow crystals, m.p. 265–67°; R_f : 30, 48(PC, 15% HOAc, BAW); λ_{max} : 255, 265, 345(MeOH); 270, 275, 325sh, 385(NaOAc) and 275, 300sh, 335sh, 425(AlCl₃); unaffected by acid hydrolysis; ir (KBr): superimposable to the spectrum of authentic luteolin-8-C-glucoside (orientin). Identity as orientin⁶ confirmed by co-tlc (R_f : 71, 60; silica gel; ethyl acetate, ethyl methyl ketone, formic acid, water = 5 : 3 : 1 : 1; ethyl acetate, methanol, water = 63 : 12 : 9) with an authentic sample.

Compound B: Light yellow needles, m.p. 250–52°; R_f : 32, 51(PC, 15% HOAc, BAW); λ_{max} : 270, 300 sh, 335(MeOH); 280, 300 sh, 370(NaOAc) and 280, 305, 345, 385(AlCl₃); unaffected by acid

hydrolysis; it is superimposable to that of authentic apigenin-8-C-glucoside (vitexin). Identity as vitexin⁶ confirmed by co-tlc (R_f : 78, 69 in the same order of solvents as A) with authentic sample.

Compound C: Light yellow solid, m.p. 210-12°; R_f : 58, 45 (PC, 15% HOAc, BAW); λ_{max} : almost the same as for A (in MeOH, NaOAc and AlCl₃); gave orientin (A) and D-glucose in 1:1 ratio on treatment with 2 N HCl or β -glucosidase. C was characterised as orientin-O'-glucoside and was indistinguishable from orientin-2'-O-glucoside⁷ by co-tlc (R_f : 28, 43) with an authentic sample.

Compound D: Light yellow solid, m.p. 216-18°; R_f : 69, 50 (PC, 15% HOAc, BAW); λ_{max} almost identical with B; yielded vitexin (B) and D-glucose in 1:1 ratio by acid as well as enzyme hydrolysis. D was characterised as vitexin-O'-glucoside and was indistinguishable from vitexin-2'-O-glucoside⁷ by co-tlc (R_f : 46, 57) with an authentic sample. (Owing to paucity of material, MS of the permethyl ether of C and D could not be run to fully establish their identities with orientin and vitexin-2'-glucosides).

M. cerviana resembles other *Mollugo* species in biosynthesising C-glycosyl flavones. However, in the place of 2'-rhamnosides of flavone-C-glucoside and arabinoside of *M. disticha* and mono and di-C-pentosyl flavones of *M. pentaphylla*, we have isolated the two common glycoflavones, orientin and vitexin along with their rare 2'-O-glucosides whose occurrence was earlier reported in *Cannabis sativa*⁸.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) with 3-Bromo-2-Hydroxy-5-Methylacetophenone Hydrazone (BHMAH)

KEEMTI LAL and (Km.) SITA RANI MALHOTRA

Department of Chemistry, D. N. College, Meerut-250 002

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A systematic spectrophotometric study of some transition metal ions complexes of 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (BHMA) and its oxime were undertaken by us with a view to investigate their chelating and other properties^{1,2}. In this note we report the use of 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone hydrazone (BHMAH) for spectrophotometric determination of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II).

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: Absorbance and pH measurements were carried out as reported earlier³. Standard stock solutions of metal ions were prepared in distilled water as described earlier³.

The ligand, BHMAH, was synthesized by refluxing BHMA¹ (0.1 mol) with hydrazinium sulphate (0.1 mol) in ethanolic medium for ~ 2 hr. The product was poured in water, filtered and crystallized from acetone, m.p. 220°. The purity of the BHMAH was checked by tlc and elemental analyses. (Found: C, 44.56; H, 4.50; N, 11.47; Br, 32.90. Calcd. for C₉H₁₁N₂OBr; C, 44.44; H, 4.52; N, 11.52; Br, 32.92%). The solution of BHMAH was prepared by dissolving on appropriate amount of the reagent in acetone.

Sodium perchlorate (Reidel) was used to maintain the ionic strength. All other solutions of cations and anions were prepared by dissolving A. R. grade chemicals in distilled water.

Procedure: An aliquot of the test solution (containing 30-50 μ g of metal ion) is transferred to a 100 ml measuring flask and excess of BHMAH solution in acetone is added. The pH of the solution is adjusted (Table 1) using suitable buffer. The total volume is made upto the mark maintaining 75% (v/v) acetone medium. The absorbance is recorded at 400 nm with the reagent solution as the blank. The amount of the metal ion is calculated from a previously calibrated graph.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves: The absorbance spectra show that the metal complexes in acetone show maximum absorbance at 400 nm.

Effect of acidity and reagent concentration: A series of solutions (metal:ligand in 1:8) varying in pH was prepared and the absorbances were recorded at 400 nm. The optimum acidity range for the complexes are given in Table 1.